

A STUDY OF ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION OF B.Ed STUDENTS

A. Sagunthala* & M. T. Udayakumar**

* M.Ed Scholar, G.E.T College of Education, Gudiyattam, Vellore, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, G.E.T College of Education, Gudiyattam, Vellore,
Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: A. Sagunthala & M. T. Udayakumar, "A Study of Achievement Motivation of B.Ed Students", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 187-191, 2017.

Abstract:

The study was aimed to study the achievement motivation B.Ed students. B.Ed students who take two years of course constitute the population of the present investigation. Out of this population, a sample of 260 students was taken for the study from Vellore district in Tamilnadu. The tool for the present study is Achievement Motivation by Pratibha Deo (Pune) and Asha Mohan (Chandigarh). National Psychological Corporation, New Delhi. Achievement Motivation has recently received considerable attention. The achievement motive involves the desire for success. It is present whenever someone is concerned with attaining some sort of standard set by him or others. This standard implies a certain degree of excellence. Thus, teachers should provide avenue for students to improve their achievement motivation by giving importance to various skills such as verbal, induction, numerical, retention and other abilities to develop the positive scientific attitude. This could be done by enriching the learning environment using different instructional techniques, materials and activities in the classroom. The finding of the study showed that there is no significant difference existed between the achievement motivation among BEd students towards gender, locality of college, mode of management, degree obtained, religion, year of study, organizational environment and type of family.

Introduction:

Achievement Motivation has recently received considerable attention. The achievement motive involves the desire for success. It is present whenever someone is concerned with attaining some sort of standard set by him or others. Achievement motivation can be seen in many areas of human endeavour on the job in school in home making or in athletic competition. Elliot (1997), People who strive for excellence in a field for the sake of achieving and not for some reward are considered to have a high need for achievement.

Motivation is generally regarded as the drive to achieve targets and the process to maintain the drive. Motivation provides an important foundation to complete cognitive behavior, such as planning, organization, decision-making, learning, and assessments (Pintrich & Schunk, 1996). Spence & Helmreich (1983) defined achievements as task-oriented behavior. Performances of individuals are often compared against standards or with others for assessments.

The differing perspectives definition of achievement motivation was from (Atkinson 1964), who defined it as the comparison of performances with others and against certain standard activities. Atkinson and Feather (1966) suggested that achievement motivation is a combination of two personality variables: tendency to approach success and tendency to avoid failure. The achievement motivation as the drive to work with diligence and vitality, to constantly steer toward targets, to obtain dominance in challenging and difficult tasks and create sense of achievement as a result. This definition consists of three elements: the stimulation of personal capabilities, constant efforts with drive and obtaining of sense of satisfaction.

Need and Importance of the Study:

Achievement motivation can be seen in many areas of human endeavour on the job in school in home making or in athletic competition. To accomplish something difficult to overcome obstacles and attain a high standard. To excel oneself, to reveal and surpass others. To increase self regard by the successful exercise of talent. Achievement motivation stem from social motives need for which we learn or acquire through social and cultural experience. The achievement motive involves desire for success. It is present whenever someone is concerned with attaining some sort of standard set by him or others. In young person the need for achievement may be expressed as a need to excel in school in college students accomplish grades and interest in problem solving

The Method adopted to collect the information /data was the normative survey. The study is descriptive in nature and residing under the head of Descriptive Research. The related data was collected with the help of a custom made Questionnaire, B.Ed students in Vellore District.

Sample:

The sample of the study consists of 260 B.Ed students from Tamilnadu in Vellore District. Simple Random Sampling method was adopted.

Statistical Treatment:

The collected data was analyzed statistically by using The Arithmetic Mean (\bar{x}), The Standard deviation (σ) and The 't' test (t). F test.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the difference if any, in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to gender.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to locality of college
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to mode of management
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to degree obtained
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to religion
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to year of study
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to organizational environment
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to type of family

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to locality of college
- ✓ There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to mode of management
- ✓ There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to degree obtained
- ✓ There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to religion
- ✓ There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to year of study
- ✓ There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to organizational environment
- ✓ There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of B.Ed students with regard to type of family

Operational Definition of Key Term Used:

Achievement motivation plays a decisive role in the organization of human behavior. It is a psychological construct which determines the achievement level of an individual. Achievement motivation is also called need for achievement.

Tool Used for the Study:

Achievement Motivation by Pratibha Deo (Pune) and Asha Mohan (Chandigarh). National Psychological Corporation, New Delhi. The scores range from 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1. The minimum score obtained can be zero and maximum can be 200.

Demographic Variables:

- ✓ Gender : Male/ Female
- ✓ Locality of School : Rural / Urban
- ✓ Mode of Management : Government / Self finance
- ✓ Degree Obtained : UG / PG / MPhil
- ✓ Religion : Hindu / Muslim / Christian
- ✓ Year of Study : I / II
- ✓ Organizational Environment : Very good / Good / Average
- ✓ Type of family : Nuclear / Joint

Analysis of Data:

Table 1: t- Test between B.Ed Students With Respect to Gender

Variable	Gender	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig
Achievement Motivation	Male	217.02	25.52	0.274	NS
	Female	217.88	24.98		

Table 1 reveals that, the Male and Female B.Ed students do not differ significantly with respect to their achievement motivation ($t=0.274, <0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. Further it is found that the male and female B.Ed students do not differ significantly in their achievement motivation.

Table 2: t- Test between B.Ed Students With Respect to Locality of College

Variable	Locality of College	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig
Achievement Motivation	Rural	217.26	25.70	0.084	NS
	Urban	217.54	24.86		

Table 2 reveals that, the rural and urban B.Ed students do not differ significantly with respect to their achievement motivation ($t=0.084, <0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. Further it is found that the rural and urban B.Ed students do not differ significantly in their achievement motivation.

Table 3: t- Test Between B.Ed Students With Respect to Mode of Management

Variable	Mode of Management	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig
Achievement Motivation	Government	217.02	25.57	0.267	NS
	Self-finance	217.86	24.94		

Table 3 reveals that, the government and self-finance of B.Ed students do not differ significantly with respect to their achievement motivation ($t=0.267, <0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. Further it is found that the government and self-finance of B.Ed students do not differ significantly in their achievement motivation.

Table 4: 'F' Value Between Sub Samples of Degree Obtained with Respect to Achievement Motivation

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Sig
Between Groups	1217.761	608.880	2	0.956	NS
Within Groups	163693.378	636.939	257		
Total	164911.138		259		

Table 4 the calculated 'F' value is 0.956, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their achievement motivation of BEd students.

Table 5: 'F' Value Between Sub Samples of Religion With Respect to Achievement Motivation

Religion	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Sig
Between Groups	853.350	426.675	2	0.668	NS
Within Groups	164057.789	638.357	257		
Total	164911.138		259		

Table 5 the calculated 'F' value is 0.668, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of religion with respect to their achievement motivation of BEd students.

Table 6: T- Test Between Bed Students With Respect to Year of Study

Variable	Year of Study	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig
Achievement motivation	I	216.20	25.75	0.831	NS
	II	218.80	24.65		

Table 6 reveals that, the I and II year of study of B.Ed students do not differ significantly with respect to their achievement motivation ($t=0.831, <0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. Further it is found that the I and II year of study of B.Ed students do not differ significantly in their achievement motivation.

Table 7: 'F' Value Between Sub Samples Of Organizational Environment With Respect to Achievement Motivation

Organizational Environment	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Sig
Between Groups	600.381	250.190	2	0.391	NS
Within Groups	164410.758	639.731	257		
Total	164911.138		259		

Table 7 the calculated 'F' value is 0.391, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of organizational environment with respect to their achievement motivation of B.Ed students.

Table 8: t -Test Between B.Ed Students With Respect Type of Family

Variable	Type of family	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig
Achievement motivation	Nuclear	217.23	25.28	0.120	NS
	Joint	217.61	25.27		

Table 8 reveals that, the nuclear family and joint family do not differ significantly with respect to their achievement motivation ($t=0.120, <0.05$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. Further it is found that the nuclear family and joint family do not differ significantly in their achievement motivation.

Major finds of the Study:

- ✓ It is found that the male and female B.Ed students do not differ significantly in their achievement motivation.

- ✓ It is found that the rural and urban B.Ed students do not differ significantly in their achievement motivation.
- ✓ It is found that the government and self-finance of B.Ed students do not differ significantly in their achievement motivation.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their achievement motivation of B.Ed students.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of religion with respect to their achievement motivation of B.Ed students.
- ✓ It is found that the I and II year of study of B.Ed students do not differ significantly in their achievement motivation.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of organizational environment with respect to their achievement motivation of B.Ed students.
- ✓ It is found that the nuclear family and joint family do not differ significantly in their achievement motivation.

Educational Implications:

- ✓ Teacher can give proper guidance and training after assessing achievement motivation to students.
- ✓ Teacher can incorporate new methods of teaching which include components of achievement motivation.
- ✓ Teacher should try to facilitate the child to develop achievement motivation and problem solving ability.
- ✓ It helps to know the effect of Achievement Motivation and Problems solving ability on curricular and co-curricular activities.
- ✓ Skill based workshops, conferences and seminars must be organized periodically to develop these skills in these areas.
- ✓ Psychological skill based activities to be promoted in teacher education institutions to promote the Achievement Motivation among the student teachers.
- ✓ Practical sessions to be given much more importance to develop the achievement motivation among the special education student teachers.
- ✓ Quality of the programme has to be still more improved to develop the achievement motivation of the student teachers.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ This study was limited to 260 B.Ed students of first and second year only.
- ✓ This study was restricted to only few colleges of vellore district from Urban and Rural colleges.

Suggestions for Further Research:

- ✓ The study could be extended to the students studying in all levels of higher education.
- ✓ Further study could be made for analyzing Achievement Motivation of the student teachers and in service teachers.
- ✓ A similar study can be undertaken by comparing problem solving ability of students.
- ✓ A similar study can be undertaken by comparing Achievement Motivation of Science and Arts students.
- ✓ A study can be undertaken to know the achievement motivation of children of high and low economic status.
- ✓ A study also can be undertaken with some more variable for higher order research.

Conclusion:

The Present study revealed that, there is significant positive correlation of Achievement Motivation. Hence from above result we can reveal that Achievement Motivation increases also. Increase and decrease in Achievement Motivation leads to decrease in of students. Hence, teacher should give importance to increase the motivation by implementing new techniques and providing rewards and prizes to students in increasing their Ability.

References:

1. Atkinson, J. & Feather, N. (1966). A theory of achievement motivation. New York: Wiley and Sons.
2. Atkinson, J. W. (1964). An introduction to motivation. New Delhi: East West Press Pvt Ltd.
3. Best John W, Khan James V. Research in Education, Tenth Edition, New Delhi. Prentice Hall of India Private Ltd, 2008.
4. Elliot, A. J., & Church, M. A. (1997). A hierarchical model of approach and avoidance achievement motivation. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 72, 218-232.
5. Garrett, Henry, Wood Worth RS. Statistics in Psychology and Education, Surjeet Publications Ltd, New Delhi, 2008.
6. Guilford JP. Fundamental Statistics in Psychology and Education New York, Mc Graw Hill Book Company Inc. 1956.

7. Guilford JP. Psychometric Methods. New York: McGraw-Hill, 1954.
8. Lokesh Koul. Methodology of Educational Research (2nd Ed) New Delhi, Vikas Publishing house Pvt. Ltd., 1990.
9. Pintrich, P. R., & Schunk D. H. (1996). Motivation in education: Theory, research, and applications. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Merrill/Prentice Hall. Psychiatry, New York: Longman Publishing Co.
10. Sindu Kulbir Singh (2006) Methodology of Research in Education. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers.
11. Spence, J. T., & Helmreich, R. L. (1983). Achievement-related motives and behavior. In J. T. Spence (Ed.), Achievement and achievement motives: Psychological and sociological approaches (pp. 10-74). San Francisco, CA: Freeman.